

LONG TERM CREEP BEHAVIOR OF A SHORT CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PEEK AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

Sylvain Corveleyn¹, Florentin Berthet², Frédéric Lachaud³, Claude Rossignol⁴

¹ Institut Clément Ader (ICA), Université de Toulouse, CNRS, Mines Albi, UPS, INSA, ISAE-SUPAERO, Campus Jarlard, 81013 Albi CT Cedex 09, France

e-mail : sylvain.corveleyn@mines-albi.fr

LIEBHERR AEROSPACE, 408 Avenue des Etats-Unis, 31016 Toulouse

e-mail : sylvain.corveleyn@liebherr.com

² Institut Clément Ader (ICA), Université de Toulouse, CNRS, Mines Albi, UPS, INSA, ISAE-SUPAERO, Campus Jarlard, 81013 Albi CT Cedex 09, France

e-mail : florentin.berthet@mines-albi.fr

³ Institut Clément Ader (ICA), Université de Toulouse, CNRS, Mines Albi, UPS, INSA, ISAE-SUPAERO, 10 Avenue Edouard Belin, 31400 Toulouse, France

e-mail : frederic.lachaud@isae.fr

⁴ LIEBHERR AEROSPACE, 408 Avenue des Etats-Unis, 31016 Toulouse

e-mail : claudio.rossignol@liebherr.com

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ABSTRACT

Short carbon fiber reinforced high performance thermoplastics, like poly (ether ether ketone) (PEEK), are materials very interesting for high temperature application. However, long term creep behaviour of this kind of material is still ill known. In this study, both quasi-static and dynamic mechanical testing are used to characterize short term and long term creep respectively at 150°C. The material is shown to behave linear viscoelastically for stresses below its elastic limit. Then a linear viscoelastic model is identified. Long term creep compliance is obtained via the time temperature superposition principle (TTSP) and well described with a Prony series. Moreover, this method allows effect of temperature and ageing determination. Nevertheless, the model underestimates viscoelastic strain if used to simulate multi steps creep/recovery tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

The high performance thermoplastic based composites sparked interest of the aeronautical industry to replace aluminum in some parts. These composites permit to produce lighter and less expensive parts. Among these materials, short carbon fiber reinforced PEEK is interesting for applications requiring high thermomechanical properties. However, the long term creep behaviour at high temperature of this material is ill known.

In this study, long term creep behaviour is described with a viscoelastic model. For polymer materials and composites, viscoelasticity can be linear or nonlinear depending on the stress applied. It is linear if there is a linear relation between stress applied and time dependent strain (i.e. $\varepsilon(t, \sigma_1 + k \cdot \sigma_2) = \varepsilon(t, \sigma_1) + k \cdot \varepsilon(t, \sigma_2)$, where k is a real, σ_1 and σ_2 are stresses and t is time). It is nonlinear else. It has been shown in literature that viscoelasticity becomes nonlinear for low stress [1, 2].

Accelerated test methods can be applied to obtain long term data from short term tests. Indeed, the time temperature superposition principle (TTSP) is used by many authors to study viscoelastic properties at long term with short-term tests at higher temperatures shifting them horizontally [3]. This method has already been applied for pure PEEK [4]. Moreover, a relation between dynamical testing and tensile creep has already shown good agreement for an epoxy resin [5].

Moreover, when a semi-crystalline and/or reinforced material, like PEEK, undergoes temperatures higher than its glass temperature (for PEEK, $T_g=143^\circ\text{C}$), it ages [6–11]. Ageing phenomena in PEEK include crystallinity increase, chains bonding and chains breakage [7, 9, 12, 13]. Those changes affect both elastic and viscoelastic behavior of the material and have to be taken into account [6, 8, 14].

2 CREEP MODELS

To model the behavior of a nonlinear viscoelastic material, the Schapery's equation is commonly used [1, 2, 15–17]:

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 \cdot D_0 \cdot \sigma(t) + g_1 \cdot \int_0^t \sum \Delta D(\Psi - \Psi') \cdot \frac{d(g_2 \sigma)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

Where D_0 is the elastic compliance and ΔD the transient compliance and $\Psi = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma}$ and $\Psi' = \int_0^\tau \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma}$ and g_0, g_1, g_2 and a_σ are non linearising functions which depend on stress applied. If the material behaves linear viscoelastically, non linearising functions are reduced to 1 and the equation becomes:

$$\varepsilon(t) = D_0 \cdot \sigma(t) + \int_0^t \sum \Delta D(t - \tau) \cdot \frac{d\sigma}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

Moreover, transient compliance is often described as a Prony series which takes into account as relaxation times as needed to describe properly the material's behaviour:

$$\Delta D(t) = \sum D_i \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau_i}\right) \right) \quad (3)$$

Where D_i is the transient compliance associated to the relaxation time τ_i .

To take into account effects of temperature and ageing on viscoelastic behavior, reduced times are used and the previous equation (2) becomes:

$$\varepsilon(t) = D_0 \cdot \sigma(t) + \int_0^t \sum \Delta D(\Psi - \Psi') \cdot \frac{d\sigma}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (4)$$

With $\Psi = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_T \cdot a_{te}}$ and $\Psi' = \int_0^\tau \frac{dt'}{a_T \cdot a_{te}}$ where a_T is the horizontal shift factor for temperature and a_{te} is the horizontal shift factor for ageing.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material used in the present study is a PEEK reinforced with 40%wt short carbon fiber provided by Victrex[®] under commercial 90HMF40. Dumbbell samples have been injection molded with a DK 65/160 machine, following the ISO527 standard (see Figure 1) with parameters shown Table 1.

T_{melt} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	420
T_{mould} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	200
P_{hold} (MPa)	80
T_{hold} (s)	12
T_{cool} (s)	55

Table 1: Injection parameters used for injection moulding the samples of this study

Figure 1: Injection molded samples used for the tensile creep study (in grey) and samples used for dynamical testing (in blue)

Material is characterized mechanically in tensile traction at 150°C with both monotonic and loading/unloading tests (see Figure 2) at strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ on an INSTRON 8862 and strain is measured with an extensometer 2620-601 having a 25mm gauge length. This way, engineering properties (elastic modulus, strain and stress at break) and plasticity and damage can be measured. Results are resumed in Figure 2 and Table 2.

Figure 2: Monotonic and loading/unloading tensile curves (left) and plastic strain and damage evolution (right) at 150°C

Elastic modulus (MPa)		Ultimate stress (MPa)		Ultimate strain (%)	
Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
19825	1137	141,4	3,5	2,13	0,31

Table 2: Engineering properties measured on 4 samples at 150°C

Creep of the material is studied in tensile traction at 150°C and under stresses below its elastic limit which was chosen as 40MPa following the mechanical characterization. A MTS tensile machine is used and strain is measured with either extensometer 634.33F-01 or strain gage which provides better results (no sliding and better accuracy). Viscoelastic behaviour is identified with a multi-steps creep/recovery test procedure (see Figure 3) [1]. Loading rate is set to $1 MPa \cdot min^{-1}$, creep steps are 4h long and recovery steps are 8h long.

Figure 3: Multi-steps creep/recovery test procedure

In the same time, dynamical tests are carried out in dual cantilever configuration on a Perkin Elmer DMA 8000. The aim is to identify long term creep compliance applying time temperature superposition principle on linear viscoelastic properties (TTSP) [3, 4]. Moreover, sample cut from aged dumbbell samples which have been aged in a ventilated oven at 320°C and 300°C for respectively 2/4/8/16/32 days and 6/12/24/48/96 days allow the calculation the shift coefficient due to ageing. Due to the limited load capacity of the machine (10N), 1mm-thick samples representative of the material are cut from the dumbbell. A frequency and temperature sweep is put into experiment for each sample. Frequency is varied from 0.01Hz to 22Hz and temperature from 25°C to 305°C and amplitude is chosen as 0.05mm. Vertical shift is applied on each storage modulus master curve to match the storage modulus at 25°C to the one measured by tensile traction tests [18].

4 RESULTS

4.1 Short term creep results

Short term tests are lead on 5 samples and the results are shown on Figure 4. Strain curves show that there is a repeatability for the two first creep/recovery steps. After, a difference is noticed and this one can be important.

Figure 4: Results obtained from multi-steps creep/recovery tests on 5 samples

For each creep steps, viscous strain normalized to stress applied is calculated ($\varepsilon_{ve}^{norm}(t) = \frac{\varepsilon_{ve}(t)}{\sigma(t)}$, where $\varepsilon_{ve}(t)$ is the viscous strain and $\sigma(t)$ is the stress applied). It is observed that the five curves are superposing well (Cf. Figure 5).

Figure 5: Viscous strain normalized to stress

This indicates that the material is linear viscoelastic. So the Schapery's equation is reduced to the equation (2). Identification of the parameters is done considering τ_i distributed logarithmically (in our case $\tau_i = 10^i$). Parameters to be identified are D_0 and D_i . Linear solver is used to find optimum parameters. Due to numerical errors, the equation has to be transformed. A integration by part leads to:

$$\varepsilon(t) = D_0 \cdot \sigma_{11}(t) + \int_0^t \sum \frac{D_i}{\tau_i} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\tau-t}{\tau_i}\right) \cdot \sigma(t) dt$$

Then the equation can be rewritten as the following system:

$$\varepsilon_{11}(t) = (\sigma_{11}(t) \quad C_1(t) \quad \dots \quad C_i(t) \quad \dots \quad C_N(t)) \begin{pmatrix} D_0 \\ D_1 \\ \vdots \\ D_i \\ \vdots \\ D_N \end{pmatrix}$$

Where $C_i(t)$ are defined at each time increment as follow:

$$C_i(t + \Delta t) = \tau_i \cdot \left[\frac{\Delta t}{2} \cdot \left(\exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_i}\right) \cdot \sigma_{11}(t) + \sigma_{11}(t + \Delta t) \right) + C_i(t) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_i}\right) \right]$$

The number of τ_i is chosen function of time increment Δt and duration of the test. Here, time increment is 0.5s and duration is 2.16e5s so τ_i were chosen as 10^i with $i \in [0,5]$. So extrapolation of the model cannot be lead for longer times than 10^6 s.

Figure 6: Identified model compared to experimental data

The model identified provides satisfactory results. However, a permanent strain is appearing and increasing during the test. This strain could be due to plasticity (i.e. plastic strain has not been seen

with loading/unloading tensile tests) or due to ageing (i.e. crystallinity increase and/or chains bonding is blocking the movement of the chains during recovery phases).

4.2 Long term creep prediction

Dynamical tests lead to results shown Figure 7. A master curve for the storage modulus at a reference temperature of 25°C is created horizontally shifting curves obtained at different temperatures.

Figure 7: Raw data (left) and master curve at the reference temperature of 25°C (right) obtained by dynamic mechanical tests

A smooth master curve is obtained and the Arrhenius graph for time shift factor is shown Figure 8.

Figure 8: Arrhenius graph for the horizontal shift factor for a reference temperature of 25°C (left) and its influence with ageing time for a reference temperature of 115°C (right)

There is little change in the storage modulus below 115°C (i.e. $\sim T_g - 30^\circ\text{C}$). This indicates that there is no significant temperature effect on the viscoelastic behavior of the material below this temperature. This is due to the mobility of macromolecular chains that is not affected under this temperature. As mentioned in [19] this temperature can be identified as T_∞ (an hypothetical temperature where all motion associated with viscous flow ceases). This temperature is around $T_g - 30^\circ\text{C}$ for many polymers. For temperatures higher than 115°C, horizontal shift factor follows an Arrhenius law. Ageing reduces the influence of temperature on shift factor (Cf. Figure 8), i.e. strain rate decrease as material is aged (because of crystallinity increase and chains bonding).

Storage modulus master curve is vertically shifted to fit with the tensile modulus measured by tensile traction test at room temperature [18]. Then, the master curve for transient compliance is obtained according to approximations described by Cai et al. [5]:

$$D_c(t) \sim \frac{1}{E(t)} \quad (5)$$

$$E(t) \cong E'(f) \Big|_{f \rightarrow \frac{1}{t}}$$

It can be identified with a Prony series and τ_i were chosen as 10^i with $i \in [-3, 38]$. Identification leads to very good results: error between model identified and experimental data is mostly less than 0.5% (Cf. Figure 9). The model identified can then be used to simulate multi-steps creep/recovery test done by tensile traction. Shift factor a_T calculated previously was used to take into account effect of temperature (Cf. Figure 10).

Figure 9: Transient creep compliance experimental data and model identified (left) and simulation of the multi-steps creep/recovery test obtained with the identified model (right)

The model identified underestimates viscous deformation, i.e. strain rate is underestimated. This can be due to the difference in test method: dual cantilever could not be compared to tensile traction.

Ageing is seen to change the storage modulus master curve (Cf. Figure 10). A horizontal shift factor could be calculated to take into account ageing on viscoelastic properties.

Figure 10: Storage modulus master curve at a temperature reference of 150°C for samples aged at 320°C for 48h, 96h, 192h, 384h and 755h

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOKS

In this work, long term creep of a short carbon fibers reinforced PEEK has been studied. Experimental study has shown the linear viscoelastic behaviour of the material below its elastic limit measured in traction. For long term prediction, dynamic mechanical testing allows a transient creep compliance master curve to be obtained. Moreover, effect of temperature and ageing can be characterized with this method. Viscoelastic model parameters are determined for short term on the multi-steps creep/recovery tests. The model leads to reliable results compared experimental data even if a permanent strain is appearing. Prony series for longer times is then identified based on the transient compliance master curve. However, some work remains to be done because this last model underestimates strain rate. Finally, long term creep test rig is currently under development to provide experimental data for durations up to 1000h to allow model comparison.

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